

Chemical Constituents of *Raupellia grata*

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A thorough chemical investigation of the Apocynaceous plant, *Raupellia grata*, having medicinal efficacies, was undertaken, since it was not chemically examined before. The investigation of the whole plant revealed the presence of a fatty matter, friedelin and epi-friedelinol. The homogeneity of the compounds, isolated, were confirmed by thin-layer chromatography.

The dried and powdered whole plant of *R. grata*, (750 gm) was extracted first with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) in a soxhlet for 48 hrs. and then percolated with 95% ethanol for one week. The petroleum extract, on removal of the solvent, gave a greenish residue (5 gm) which when chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (125 gm) gave three distinct products on eluting with different solvents. The petroleum ether eluate gave a waxy solid, m.p. 82-85°, which was not investigated further. The earlier fractions of the benzene eluates furnished a solid, m.p. 246-50° (1.5 gm), which responded to the triterpenes colour reactions. Several crystallisations of this solid from petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°) gave fine needles, m.p. 259-61°, (α)_D³⁰ -28° (CHCl₃), [Found : C, 83.92, H, 11.55; Calculated for C₃₀H₅₀O : C, 84.50; H, 11.74%]. It showed a negative test with tetranitromethane and was identified as friedelin by mixed m.p. (Lit.^{1,2} m.p. 260-62°, (α)-29°), I.R. 5.85 μ for a six-membered ring ketone) and N.M.R. characteristics (the CDCl₃ solution exhibits signals of the tertiary methyl groups at 0.76, 0.90, 0.98, 1.02, 1.05, 1.19 and 1.39 ppm, with secondary methyl doublet centered at about 0.88 ppm,) with an authentic sample of friedelin. The identity with friedelin was further confirmed by the preparation of its oxime, m.p. 290-92° (Lit.² m.p. 290-94°), oxime acetate, m.p. 235-37° (Lit.² m.p. 237-39°) and borohydride reduction products — friedelinol, m.p. 301° (Lit.^{3,4} m.p. 303-06°) and epi-friedelinol, m.p. 279° (Lit. m.p.^{3,4} 280-82°).

Later fractions of the benzene eluates, on concentration, furnished a solid, m.p. 265-70° (300 mg), which gave a positive Libermann-Burchardt test for triterpene but no colouration with tetranitromethane. Several crystallisations of the solid from chloroform-methanol (1 : 1) gave hexagonal plates, m.p. 280-82°, (α)_D³⁰ +20° (CHCl₃), [Found : C, 83.92; H, 11.93; Calculated for C₃₀H₅₂O : C, 84.11; H, 12.15%]. It was identified as epifriedelinol by m.m.p. (Lit.^{5,6} m.p. 278-80°, (α)_D +21°) and I.R. characteristics (2.85 μ). The identity was further established by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 290-92°, (α)_D + 34° (Lit.⁷ m.p. 290-94°, (α)_D + 45°).

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The defatted plant material was percolated with 95% ethanol for seven days. The solvent was removed under low pressure, and the residue was taken in chloroform (300 ml). The chloroform solution was washed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (1%, 3 × 50 ml). The aqueous acidic solution was worked up for the basic material when neither any solid could be isolated nor any tests for alkaloid could be obtained. The dry chloroform solution on removal of the solvent gave a gummy residue from which no crystalline material could be isolated.

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. Mukherjee of the Air Force Research Laboratory, Massachusetts, U.S.A., for I.R. and N.M.R. spectra, to Dr. G. Ganguli of Duke University, Durham, North Carolina, U.S.A., for helpful discussion, to Dr. D. P. Chakrabarty of Bose Institute, Calcutta for rotation and to Sri R. N. Chakrabarty of the University College of Science, Calcutta for microanalysis. Thanks are due to the University Grants Commission New Delhi, for the award of a Research Training Scholarship to one of us (S.D.).

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Received, April 23, 1968.